

Exploring the leadership quotient and school leader's performance in primary education

Jovelyn V. Pestaño¹, Rayvin D. Pestaño²

¹DepEd-CLSU Elementary (Lab.) School, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz Nueva Ecija, Philippines

²ISPELS-College of Education, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz Nueva Ecija, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Apr 20, 2024

Revised Jul 11, 2024

Accepted Aug 28, 2024

Keywords:

Adversity quotient

Leader's performance

Leadership quotient

Primary education

School leader's

ABSTRACT

This study attempts to investigate the leadership quotient (LQ) and adversity quotient (AQ) of school leaders in elementary school and its influence on their performance. School leaders' performance was measured using the office performance and review forms rating. The study employed a descriptive quantitative correlational research design. Through survey questionnaire, data were collected from 43 respondents via total enumeration sampling. Results showed that the school heads exhibit high LQ, particularly in the components of inspiring trust, clarifying purpose, aligning system, unleashing talent and high AQ in the dimension of control, ownership, reach, and endurance. Consequently, all school leaders received outstanding performance evaluations. The study's key findings suggest that LQ components such as inspire trust, clarify purpose, align system and unleash talent, and AQ dimensions including control and ownership positively influence school leaders' performance, indicating the importance of these factors in school leadership. Recommendations for school leaders include conducting self-evaluation, engaging in seminars and workshops, participating in mentoring and coaching programs. Further studies on the factors that predict the LQ in school leaders and its impact on school performance are suggested to contribute to the educational field.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Rayvin D. Pestaño

ISPELS-College of Education, Central Luzon State University

Science City of Muñoz Nueva Ecija, Philippines

Email: rayvin.pestano@clsu2.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

In the Department of Education, school leaders serve as pivotal figures within the educational system. They are responsible in providing leadership in the development and implementation of all educational programs and projects in the school. As stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 32 s. 2010, school heads shall be competent, committed, and accountable in providing access to quality education for all through transformational leadership and high degree of professionalism. Furthermore, in Republic Act No. 9155, Chapter 1 Section No. 7, Letter E, Paragraph 3, consistent with the national educational policies, plans and standards, the school heads shall have the authority, responsibility and accountability in managing all affairs of the school. Thus, school leaders' leadership is imperative towards school improvement [1].

Educational leadership is an integral characteristic of school effectiveness [2]. Since school principals are involved in all aspects of the school operation, it is necessary to constantly improve their professional leadership and personal traits such as intelligence quotient (IQ) and emotional quotient (EQ) to successfully manage the school. Moreover, effective leadership entails another quotient, leadership quotient (LQ) [3]. LQ suggests that leaders must possess knowledge on how to act, along with the discernment of when to act based

considering the attributes of oneself, followers, and the environments in which they operate [4]. Hence, LQ can be construed as essential element to measure and improve one's leadership [3].

As the forerunners of educational institution, school heads should portray excellence in leadership to carry out the duties for the successful management of the school [5]–[7], and improve quality of education [8]. As their role has become more complex and multifaceted, they need to deal with problems concerning the various aspects of school leadership. Consequently, with these responsibilities and accountabilities linked with the position of being a school head, conflict, crisis, and adversity are often experienced.

In the lens of school leaders, adversity can be considered as an obstacle in achieving the desired goals, outcomes and vision of an institution. Conversely, adversity can be an opportunity to strengthen one's skills in order to withstand or overcome the adverse circumstances within the scope of school supervisory and management [9]. Learning to deal with adversity is a significant element of effective management [10]. This ability to overcome hardships is labelled as the adversity quotient (AQ). AQ as defined by Stoltz [11], centers on a person's capabilities to effectively manage difficulties and transform obstacles into opportunities. Thus, it is necessary for a school leader to have a high degree of AQ to resolve specific school related concerns and challenges that will contribute to improved school performance.

School head's performance is vital for the quality delivery of educational services to its clientele. In the Philippine educational system, the Department of Education offers provision to assess the work performance of school head (office performance commitment and review form (OPCRF)) to monitor school targets and accomplishments. It provides verifiable basis for measuring performance rating which are categorized based on the following: 4.50-5.00 for outstanding, 3.50-4.49 for very satisfactory, 2.50-3.49 for satisfactory, 1.50-2.49 for unsatisfactory, and below 1.49 for poor. Tansiongco and Ibarra [9] contends that school leaders' performance is most effectively assessed through OPCRF ratings. Several studies have been conducted that utilized OPCRF as a measure that depicted school leaders' performance [12]–[14]. While recent studies have delved into various aspects of school leadership, including practices [15]–[17], styles [12], [18], [19], skills [20]–[22], and competence [23], there remains a notable gap in the exploration of LQ and its impact with school leader's performance.

The study aimed to determine the LQ, AQ, and its relationship to the school leader's performance in the Schools Division of Angeles City, Pampanga, Philippines. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: i) how may the LQ, AQ and performance of school leaders be described? ii) is there a significant relationship between LQ, AQ and work performance of school leaders? and iii) what plan of action may be proposed to improve the school leader's performance?

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

In this study, descriptive correlational research design was utilized to determine the relationship between LQ and school leaders' performance. According to Wiersma and Jurs [24], designing a study helps researchers to plan and implement the study in a way that will help them obtain the intended results, thus, increasing the chances of obtaining information that could be associated with the real situation.

2.2. Locale and respondents

The respondents of this study were the 43 elementary school heads in the Division of Angeles City, Pampanga, Philippines. This study employed the total enumeration sampling technique, also known as total population sampling. According to Lavrakas [25], total population sampling is a category of purposive sampling wherein the whole population of interest (i.e., a group whose members all share a given characteristic) is studied and specifically when the population is relatively small and where each sample is of significant importance.

2.3. Data collection instruments

In gathering the data, the researchers found that two comprehensive questionnaires genuinely developed by Covey [26] and Stoltz [11] were very suitable and useful for data analysis to address the research problems. The survey questionnaire comprised of three different parts; Part 1 consist of 39 items with a 5-point Likers scale from very high (5) to very low (1). Part 2 composed of 20 items with the same 5-point Likert scale. Part 3 contains school leaders' performance using of OPCRF. The questionnaire was designed to measure the LQ, AQ, and performance of the respondents.

2.4. Data analysis

The data collected were tabulated and analyzed using statistical package for the social science software volume 21. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the school leader's performance via OPCRF.

Furthermore, weighted mean was utilized to described the LQ and AQ. While Pearson correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between LQ, AQ, and performance of school leaders.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. School leader’s performance

The school heads’ work performance based on the OPCRF results is presented in Table 1. It can be seen from the Table 1 that 43 or 100% of the school heads obtained an “outstanding” rating. As stated on the National Competency-based Standards for School Heads (NCBSSH), an effective school head is one who can implement continuous school improvement, who can produce better learning outcomes among its pupils/students and who can help change institutional culture among others. Indeed, the success and failure of an organization greatly depends on the performance of the leaders [27]. Thus, it is imperative that school leaders outstanding performance be sustained through continuous motivation to benefit the school’s and its stakeholders in particular [12].

Table 1. Performance of school leaders

Performance (OPCRF)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	43	100
Very satisfactory	0	0
Satisfactory	0	0
Unsatisfactory	0	0
Poor	0	0

Legend: poor 1.00-1.49; unsatisfactory 1.50-2.49; satisfactory 2.50-3.49; very satisfactory 3.50-4.49; outstanding 4.50-5.00

3.2. Correlation of leadership quotient and school leader’s performance

3.2.1. Inspire trust leadership quotient and school leader’s performance

School leaders in the Schools Division of Angeles City, Pampanga have very high level of LQ in terms of inspire trust based on the mean and standard deviation of 4.70±0.22. It can be seen in Table 2 that a significant relationship has been found between inspire trust (LQ) and performance of school leaders with a p-value of 0.02. This relationship likely indicates that trust can positively impacts work performance and is of vital importance both in leadership and student outcomes [28], [29]. Conversely, Tsachannen-Moran and Gareis [30] give emphasis on the vital role of fostering and maintaining trust in successful school leadership.

3.2.2. Clarify purpose leadership quotient and school leader’s performance

The findings on clarify purpose were revealed to be very high level of LQ with a mean and standard deviation of 4.80±0.28. Table 2 shows that a significant relationship is established between clarify purpose (LQ) and school leaders’ performance with a p-value of 0.02. This connection implies that school leaders prioritize ensuring that individuals understand how their efforts contribute to the broader mission and vision of the school. Tyler [31] underscores the values of communication skills of school leaders in school management. More so, effective patterns of communication such as explaining the purpose behind tasks and initiatives, school leaders empower their internal and external stakeholders to align their efforts with organizational goals, ultimately leading to improved work performance [32].

3.2.3. Align systems leadership quotient and school leader’s performance

As shown in Table 2, align systems LQ disclosed also as very high with a mean and standard deviation of 4.76±0.22. Moreover, results in Table 2 disclosed a significant relationship was found between align systems (LQ) and performance of school leaders. Findings indicates that school leaders design systems and processes to facilitate progress, regardless of their direct involvement can influence performance. Farrell [33] noted that designing and aligning school systems play a critical role in supporting schools and educators. Furthermore, Manley and Hawkins [34] assert that designing effective school systems involves monitoring, assessing, and improving all processes in the schools. Thus, aligning system helps school leaders in improving practices and policies that foster a culture of high performance.

Table 2. Descriptive and correlational values of LQ and school leader’s performance

LQ	N	Mean±SD	Description	p-value (Sig. 2 tailed)	Interpretation
Inspire trust	43	4.70±0.22	Very high	0.002**	Significant
Clarify purpose	43	4.80±0.28	Very high	0.002**	Significant
Align systems	43	4.76±0.22	Very high	0.009**	Significant
Unleash talent	43	4.84±0.24	Very high	0.002**	Significant

Legend: very low 1.00-1.80, low 1.81-2.60, average 2.61-3.40, high 3.41-4.20, very high 4.21-5.00

3.2.4. Unleash talent leadership quotient and school leader's performance

It can be noticed in Table 2 that school leaders unleash talent LQ were disclosed to be very high with a mean and standard deviation of 4.84 ± 0.24 . This connection likely suggests that school leaders consistently embody the principles of unleashing, empowering, and supporting individuals to achieve desired outcomes. Kilag *et al.* [35] asserts that empowering management of school leaders have a direct and profound impacts on teachers and school effectiveness. Therefore, school leaders are expected to continuously supports and empower teachers and students [36].

3.3. Correlation of adversity quotient and school leader's performance

3.3.1. Control adversity quotient and school leader's performance

Table 3 illustrates the AQ of the respondents, control dimension (AQ) was found to be high with a mean and standard deviation of 4.01 ± 0.24 . Moreover, a significant relationship has been found as to control dimension (AQ) and school leaders' performance. Results likely suggests that school leaders perceived that they have significantly greater control and influence, especially in challenging situations. Findings also implies that school leaders with high control AQ will more likely take positive actions that will improve the achievement of the schools [37]. Similarly, Napire [38] determined that control dimension (AQ) can positively influenced institutional performance along with leadership and governance.

3.3.2. Ownership adversity quotient and school leader's performance

Findings disclosed a very high AQ of school leaders' respondents in ownership with a mean and standard deviation of 4.28 ± 0.23 . Table 3 revealed a significant relationship between ownership dimension (AQ) and performance of school leaders. This relationship likely indicates that school leaders who take ownership of their responsibilities tend to have better work performance. Leaders that shared accountability and responsibility among other school member may lead to improvement in performance and an essential element of school governance [39], [40]. Thus, school head's role is essential for ensuring the advancement and effectiveness of education system [41].

3.3.3. Reach adversity quotient, endurance adversity quotient, and school leader's performance

It can be noticed in Table 3 that AQ in the dimensions of reach and endurance were also found as high with a mean of standard deviation of 3.91 ± 0.26 with the former and 4.10 ± 0.23 with the latter. Results indicates that reach dimension (AQ) and endurance dimension (AQ) had no significant relationship with the performance of school leaders. While these dimensions of AQ are valuable aspects of personal resilience, it may not directly influence the performance of school leaders due to the complex nature of educational leadership roles and the multifaceted challenges encounter. On the other hand, Verma *et al.* [42] emphasized the need for individuals to maintain a high degree of AQ to become more effective and efficient in the workplace.

Table 3. Descriptive and correlational values of AQ and school leader's performance

AQ	N	Mean±SD	Description	p-value (Sig. 2 tailed)	Interpretation
Control	43	4.01±0.24	High	0.001**	Significant
Ownership	43	4.28±0.23	Very high	0.046*	Significant
Reach	43	3.91±0.26	High	0.345	Insignificant
Endurance	43	4.10±0.23	High	0.305	Insignificant

Legend: very low 1.00-1.80, low 1.81-2.60, average 2.61-3.40, high 3.41-4.20, very high 4.21-5.00

4. CONCLUSION

The results from the data collection shows that LQ of the school leaders were found to be very high in all area; inspire trust (LQ), clarify purpose (LQ), align systems (LQ), and unleash talent (LQ). In terms of AQ, ownership (AQ) dimension was found to be very high, while control (AQ), reach (AQ) and endurance (AQ) were perceived as high by the respondents. As to the school leader's performance, all school leaders disclosed that their performance rating were outstanding performance based on their OPCRf rating.

Findings revealed that LQs areas such as inspire trust (LQ), clarify purpose (LQ), align systems (LQ) and unleash talent (LQ) have a positive influence on school leader's performance. In terms of AQ (AQ) dimension, results shows that control (AQ) and ownership (AQ) dimension have a positive impact on their performance. While reach (AQ) and endurance (AQ) dimension do not affect school leaders' performance.

Some limitations were identified in the present study that could be translated into research opportunities. First of all, the present study focused on internal factors such as LQ and AQ. Other internal and external factors that may influence the performance of school leaders such as resiliency and motivation (internal) and concerns, work environment etc. (external) may be explored. Other researchers are encouraged

to investigate these areas. Another limitation to put on emphasis is the generalizability of research samples. While, school leaders can share almost the same characteristics in terms of leadership and AQ, individual differences still exist. It is hoped, therefore that future researchers can explore gender roles and collect more samples from other divisions to improve the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, studies on the factors that predict the LQ in school heads and its impact on work performance, and correlation between LQ and school performance are suggested to contribute to the educational field.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hargreaves and D. Fink, "Sustaining leadership," *Phi Delta Kappan*, vol. 84, no. 9, pp. 693–700, May 2003, doi: 10.1177/003172170308400910.
- [2] A. Kythreotis, P. Pashiardis, and L. Kyriakides, "The influence of school leadership styles and culture on students' achievement in cyprus primary schools," *Journal of Educational Administration*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 218–240, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1108/09578231011027860.
- [3] B. Bill Service and D. Arnott, *The leadership quotient: 12 dimensions for measuring and improving leadership*. iUniverse, 2006.
- [4] M. J. Fekula and R. W. Service, "Assessing emotional intelligence: the eq matrix exercise," in *Developments in Business Simulation and Experiential Learning*, 2007.
- [5] N. Mustamin and M. A. M. Bin Yasin, "The competence of school principals: what kind of need competence for school success?," *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 33–42, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.11591/edulearn.v6i1.188.
- [6] A. Androniceanu, B. Ristea, and M. M. Uda, "Leadership competencies for project based school management success," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 182, pp. 232–238, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.760.
- [7] J. Welch and M. Hodge, "Assessing impact: the role of leadership competency models in developing effective school leaders," *School Leadership and Management*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 355–377, 2018, doi: 10.1080/13632434.2017.1411900.
- [8] N. A. Salfi, "Successful leadership practices of head teachers for school improvement: some evidence from Pakistan," *Journal of Educational Administration*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 414–432, 2011, doi: 10.1108/09578231111146489.
- [9] L. A. Tansiongco and F. Ibarra, "Educational leader's adversity quotient, management style, and job performance: implications to school leadership," *Indonesian Research Journal in Education (IRJE)*, pp. 386–401, 2020, doi: 10.22437/irje.v4i2.9264.
- [10] L. D. Canivel, "Principals' adversity quotient: styles, performance, and practices," University of the Philippines, 2010.
- [11] P. G. Stoltz, *Adversity quotient: turning obstacles into opportunities*. Morrow, New York, 2000.
- [12] B. T. Mangulabnan, R. I. Dela Rosa, and D. S. Vargas, "Effects of leadership styles and conflict management strategies to school performance in the Philippines," *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, vol. 6, no. 8, pp. 7638–7657, 2022, [Online]. Available: <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/11113>
- [13] M. A. M. Temprosa, "Strategic priorities, management competencies, and performance of the divisions of schools in Negros Island, Philippines," *Philippine Social Science Journal*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 82–90, 2021, doi: 10.52006/main.v4i4.443.
- [14] P. Ramsey and C. Belencion, "Management action and organizational performance of public elementary schools," *Research Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 31–60, 2020.
- [15] C. J. C. Aquino, B. T. Afalla, and F. L. Fabelico, "Managing educational institutions: school heads' leadership practices and teachers' performance," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1325–1338, 2021, doi: 10.11591/IJERE.V10I4.21518.
- [16] M. K. F. D. Aya, L. P. Buenvenida, C. S. Tan, M. M. Bandoy, and K. A. Manaig, "Leadership practices, adversity quotient, and school-based management practices in the new normal: a descriptive-correlational approach," *International Journal of Theory and Application in Elementary and Secondary School Education*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 59–84, 2022, doi: 10.31098/ijtaese.v4i2.1091.
- [17] M. B. Cahapay, "The phenomenon of leading without guidebook: educational leadership practices of Philippine school principals in virulent COVID-19 times," *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.17583/ijelm.0.7666.
- [18] S. S. Rana, N. I. Malik, and R. Y. Hussain, "Leadership styles as predictors of job involvement in teachers," *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 161–182, 2016.
- [19] K. Parveen, P. Quang Bao Tran, T. Kumar, and A. H. Shah, "Impact of principal leadership styles on teacher job performance: an empirical investigation," *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 7, 2022, doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.814159.
- [20] J. Schulz, M.-A. Mundy, and D. Jones, "A comparison of practical leadership skills of principals and assistant principals," *National Forum of Educational Administration and Supervision Journal*, vol. 34, 2016.
- [21] G. B. De Castro and E. C. Jimenez, "Influence of school principal's attributes and 21st-century leadership skills on teachers' performance," *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 52–63, 2022, doi: 10.36079/lamintang.jhass-0402.374.
- [22] K. Webster and P. Litchka, "Planning for effective school leadership: teachers' perceptions of the leadership skills and ethical behaviors of school principals," *Educational Planning*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 31–47, 2020, [Online]. Available: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1250500>
- [23] T. M. Kin, O. A. Kareem, M. S. Nordin, and K. W. Bing, "Principal change leadership competencies and teacher attitudes toward change: the mediating effects of teacher change beliefs," *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 427–446, 2018, doi: 10.1080/13603124.2016.1272719.
- [24] W. Wiersma and S. G. Jurs, *Research methods in education: An introduction (9th ed.)*. Pearson Education, 2009.
- [25] P. Lavrakas, *Encyclopedia of survey research methods 1st edition*. 2008.
- [26] F. Covey, *Leadership quotient tm report for: sample report introduction to the LQ1 report*. 2007.
- [27] A. E. Eide, E. A. Saether, and A. Aspelund, "An investigation of leaders' motivation, intellectual leadership, and sustainability strategy in relation to Norwegian manufacturers' performance," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 254, p. 120053, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120053.
- [28] P. R. Wood, "The impact of trust on school principals' leadership," Durham University, 2014.
- [29] P. Kwan, "The effect of trust on the relationship between instructional leadership and student outcomes in Hong Kong secondary schools," *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 111–121, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s40299-015-0242-5.
- [30] M. Tschannen-Moran and C. R. Gareis, "Faculty trust in the principal: an essential ingredient in high-performing schools," *Journal of Educational Administration*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 66–92, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1108/JEA-02-2014-0024.

- [31] D. E. Tyler, "Communication behaviors of principals at high performing title I elementary schools in Virginia: school leaders, communication, and transformative efforts," *Creighton Journal of Interdisciplinary Leadership*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 2, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.17062/cjil.v2i2.51.
- [32] C. O. Fashiku, "Leaders' communication pattern: a predictor of lecturers' job performance in Nigeria," *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 103–126, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.17583/ijelm.2016.1848.
- [33] C. C. Farrell, "Designing school systems to encourage data use and instructional improvement," *Educational Administration Quarterly*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 438–471, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1177/0013161X14539806.
- [34] R. J. Manley and R. Hawkins, *Designing school systems for all students: a toolbox to fix america's schools*. 2009.
- [35] O. K. Kilag *et al.*, "School leaders: the extent of management empowerment and its impact on teacher and school effectiveness," *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 127–140, 2023, [Online]. Available: <https://multijournals.org/index.php/excellencia-imje/article/view/13>
- [36] A. Balyer, K. Özcan, and A. Yildiz, "Teacher empowerment: school administrators roles," *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 17, no. 70, pp. 1–18, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.14689/ejer.2017.70.1.
- [37] P. N. Okorji and F. Epetuku, "Relationship between principals adversity quotient and leadership styles in secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria," *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, vol. 9, no. 7, p. p91123, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.29322/IJSRP.9.07.2019.p91123.
- [38] J. N. Napire, "Adversity quotient® and management skills of school principals: their influence on institutional performance," 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.peaklearning.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/PEAK_GRI_Napire_April-2019.pdf
- [39] L. A. Unda, Z. Gong, K. Benati, and C. M. Loh, "Role expectations and shared accountability: a framework for school governance," *Financial Accountability and Management*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 790–808, 2023, doi: 10.1111/faam.12322.
- [40] S. Maile, "Accountability: an essential aspect of school governance," *South African journal of education*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 326–331, 2002.
- [41] G. ten Bruggencate, H. Luyten, J. Scheerens, and P. Sleegers, "Modeling the influence of school leaders on student achievement," *Educational Administration Quarterly*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 699–732, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1177/0013161X11436272.
- [42] S. Verma, A. Aggarwal, and H. Bansal, "The relationship between emotional intelligence (EQ) and adversity quotient (AQ)," *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, vol. 19, no. 01, pp. 49–53, 2017, doi: 10.9790/487x-1901024953.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Jovelyn V. Pestaño is a classroom teacher in DepEd-CLSU Elementary (Lab.) School, Central Luzon State University. She received her bachelor's degree at Polytechnic University of the Philippines-Cabiao Campus, and her master's degree, master of educational management at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology. She is currently pursuing her masters of arts in education with specialization in special education at the College of Immaculate Conception-Cabanatuan City. Her research interests also include educational leadership, school management, pedagogy and learning in elementary grades and special education. She can be contacted at email: jovelyn.velasquez@deped.gov.ph.

Rayvin D. Pestaño is an associate professor at the Institute of Sports, Physical Education and Leisure Studies, College of Education, Central Luzon State University, Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija. He received his doctor of philosophy in Development Education degree at CLSU, and his master of arts in education with specialization in physical education at the College of Immaculate Conception-Cabanatuan City. Presently, he is pursuing his masters of arts in education with specialization in special education at CIC. His research interest includes educational management in sports, development education, physical education, and sports. He publishes scholarly articles in the field of education. He can be contacted at email: rayvin.pestano@clsu2.edu.ph.